

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 ISSN: 2091-5004 № ISSUE 11 30.11.2024

ME'MORCHILIK VA QURILISH MUAMMOLARI

(ilmiy -texnik jurnal) 30.11.2024 № 11-son

ПРОБЛЕМЫ АРХИТЕКТУРЫ И СТРОИТЕЛЬСТВА

(научно-технический журнал) 30.11.2024 № ВЫПУСК-1

Jurnal OAK Hay'atining qaroriga binoan texnika (qurilish, mexanika va mashinasozlik sohalari) fanlari hamda me'morchilik bo'yicha ilmiy maqolalar chop etilishi lozim bo'lgan ilmiy jurnallar ro'yxatiga kiritilgan (guvohnoma №00757. 2000.31.01)

Jurnalimizdagi ingliz tilida chop etilgan maqolalar OAK Rayosatining 2020 yil 30 iyuldagi 283/7.1-son qaroriga asosan xorijiy ilmiy nashrlarda chop etilgan ilmiy maqolalarga teng lashtirilganini ma'lum qiladi.

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PLANNING OF HOUSING CONSTRUCTION IN THE INNER-DISTRICT AREA

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Abstract: The first and second groups of the population spend their entire time in the territory of the microdistrict. About 60% of preschool children are in kindergartens (except Sunday). Junior School students spend almost half of the day in the playing fields of the microdistrict. Preschool children usually walk close to homes accompanied by adults. In summer, more than 80% of children travel out of town (summer houses, camps). Most of the time is spent by pensioners in the microdistrict (20% with children, 60% with independent rest). Adults and young people are absent from the territory of the microdistrict on weekdays, and the use of accommodation by them is minimal.

Key words: Residential areas, microdistricts, zoning.

Residential area-plots with enterprises, cultural and domestic residential buildings or groups of service enterprises, schools and courtyards, which are combined with kindergartens;

several residential buildings (4-5) and zoning of active and passive form an area of 0.8-2.5 hectares.the recreation areas, taking into account plot between two or three buildings, various groups of the population;

the area of which does not exceed 0.5- isolation of an active and quiet 0.7 hectares, is usually called a recreation area from development;

landscaped courtyard. For the - the use of relief forms, the construction of the garden, choose the creation of terraces, protective walls, convenient descent and installation of approaches to buildings, public stairs, slides due to the ground removed from the pits of buildings;

planning project: rational design of convenient decorating blind concrete facades pedestrian connections and with climbing plants;

approaches to buildings, public - isolation of recreation areas from transport stops, commercial development with the help of

plantations, opening views of the microdistrict Community Center;

separation of planning axes and composition centers in the form of alleys, ponds, architectural monuments;

saturation of the residential area with small architectural forms and elements of artistic expression of external landscaping for various purposes;

garden-individualization of courtyard gardens of groups of residential buildings by enriching the garden landscape, saturating it with spectacular ornamental plants throughout the season.

The development of a planning solution for landscaping is carried out taking into account the needs of the population, meeting the requirements in daily rest, movement and economic activities. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that the residential areas in space are small in size and limited.

In order to better organize the territory, it is necessary to determine the interests the population is in its use.

The entire population of the residential district is divided into the following age groups:

1) preschool children (up to 6 years old);

2) junior school students (ages 7-13);

3) middle and senior school students (ages 14-17);

4) working adult population and student youth;

5) pensioners.

The first and second groups of the population spend their entire time in the territory of the microdistrict. About 60% of preschool children are in kindergartens (except Sunday). Junior School students spend almost half of the day in the playing fields of the microdistrict. Preschool children usually walk close to homes accompanied by adults. In summer, more than 80% of children travel out of town (summer houses, camps). Most of the time is spent by pensioners in the microdistrict (20% with children, 60% with independent rest). Adults and young people are absent from the territory of the microdistrict on weekdays, and the use of accommodation by them is minimal.

Based on the needs of the population, taking into account the interests of different groups of the population, the entire residential area is divided into appropriate functional zones.

In order to correctly and purposefully develop the planning solution of the construction area and

its improvement, it is necessary to carry out functional zoning.

In accordance with the step-by-step system of serving the population and in order to ensure maximum comfort in the microdistrict, the following are distinguished:

residential area, including all residential buildings intended for landscaping, adjacent corridors, corridors, pedestrian paths, pedestrian paths, communal, children's, courtyard-gardens with sports fields;

the zone of school institutions, including a school building, an entrance, a school area with educational-experimental plots and a sports core, as well as recreation areas and a farm yard;

zone of preschool institutions-kindergartens-kindergartens. This zone includes the building of the institution itself, a plot with a set of recreation and playgrounds, a farm yard, a vegetable garden, a greenhouse;

zone of cultural and domestic institutions. It includes buildings (clubs, household workshops, etc.), plots in front of them, approaches and entrances;

economic space-approaches to garages, parking lots, utility block, boiler room, entrances and buildings, their surroundings.

Close to residential buildings are entrances and entrances to buildings,

front gardens on the opposite side of the building (adjacent lines) (8-10 m wide), from the ends of the buildings (6-8 m wide), an area located on the side of the entrances, but outside the passage (20-30 m wide).). This zone is the center of the main areas of use of the population, where recreation areas for preschool children, recreation areas for pensioners, places of economic activity (cleaning carpets, drying laundry, litter boxes) should be placed.

In the center of the courtyard of the Residential Group, an open recreation area is allocated, where it is necessary to provide sports and play facilities for school-age children and partially for young people and adults.

In the scheme of functional zoning of the residential area, zones of calm rest, economic activity and outdoor recreation are distinguished. On the basis of such zoning, first of all, a planning solution is developed, which provides for the placement of various types of territories with a set of equipment. It should be remembered that the maximum effect of landscaping the territory and seedlings depends on the successful placement of the territories. In this case, it is necessary to take into account the radius of service to the population (the maximum distance from the entrance to the territory).

The favorable location of areas in the allocated zones contributes to the normal growth and development of seedlings. If the areas are placed without taking into account the needs of the population and the radius of service, experience shows that seedlings are trampled; residents independently organize recreation areas or housing plots directly on lawns and do not use inconveniently located areas. As a result, the seedlings suffer and the entire area becomes irregular appearance.

All the grounds of the residential area are divided into:

for children-for preschool children, the service radius is 25-50 m;

for children-for Primary School students, the service radius is up to 50-100 m;

sports-service radius for high school students, youth and adults up to 200-300 m;

quiet adult REST, service radius up to 50 m;

Economic, Service radius up to 100 m;

complex areas (sectional complexes) in the gardens of residential groups.

The number and size of the regions, as well as their visit, are calculated depending on the number and age composition of the population (approximate ratio).

The size of all categories of territories is calculated based on the simultaneous presence of the population, their children, youth and adult participation.

To determine the size of areas intended for various purposes for a particular area, first of all, calculate the number of residents of this group of houses based on the general technical and economic indicators of residential buildings (series of houses, number of apartments). The population of each age group is then determined. In addition, calculate the dimensions of each area using approximate norms for the use of territories for each person.

The number of residents in the house is determined on the basis of a number of buildings.

the number of residents in each House determines the number of residents in the residential group.

Places for children under 3 years of age and between 4 and 7 years of age can be combined to highlight corners for the little ones (parents with strollers). Such areas should be placed close to houses, but not closer than 15-20 m from the windows of buildings.

It is allowed to combine territories for preschool children with recreation areas for adults or places for young children (in the conditions of high-density buildings). Such complex areas are evenly spaced across the entire

area from the entrance of the houses. When designing, appropriate zoning of the territory of the territory is recommended.

In relatively large (0.8-2.5 ha) garden-courtyards, small groups of residential buildings should provide typical sectional (play) complexes for children 4-6 and 7-14 years old. In this case, places for children under 3 years old should be placed close to residential premises. When placing territories, determining their number and size, it is necessary to take into account the climatic features of the territory that directly affect the visit.

Observations in different cities show that in the conditions of the middle lane, the entire number of residents who Rest in the regions is distributed as follows,%: young people and adults — 8, pensioners — 12, children under 14 — 80. At one time, the number of vacationers in residential microdistricts of St. Petersburg is 20%, and in Yerevan microdistricts-30% of the entire population. In playgrounds, these fluctuations increase by 1.5-2.0 times. Playgrounds must have appropriate equipment. Sample equipment albums and norms of their use have been developed by Project organizations in Moscow, Kiev, St. Petersburg.

For high school students, young people and adults, sports fields should

be placed at a distance of at least 20-40 m from the walls of the nearest buildings with Windows, the dimensions of these areas are determined according to standards. When designing sports fields, it is necessary to take into account the radius of service up to 200 m.volleyball, basketball and tennis courts should be combined into blocks surrounded by a special metal mesh with a height of 3 m. individual platforms inside the block are also separated by a fence (height of 1.2 m).

It is recommended to place sports fields in well—ventilated and slightly elevated areas, directing them along the meridian (S-yu) with a long axis.

In the gardens of residential groups, places for peaceful recreation and table games for adult residents are located close to residential buildings, as well as on transport routes, close to household service institutions, shops, etc.

The dimensions of the recreation areas of the adult population are not regulated, but they should not be developed in a very large size. The Optimal size is 25-75 m².

The farm grounds are located close to the buildings, but not closer than 15-20 m.

Places for drying clothes should be separated from cleaning areas and litter boxes.

When designing, lighting should be taken into account: places for drying and cleaning things require maximum radiation, and for litter boxes — shade.

The road network serves as an addition to the network of roads, roads, lanes. The width of the track is multiplied by 0.75 m (the width of movement of one person), it should be increased to 1.5 m at the places of installation of benches.

All roads are classified according to the purpose, depending on the intensity of transport.

Lowest permitted groundwater levels in spring-

the autumn period under the surface of the roads is 0.8 m for sandy soils, 1.3—1.5 m for pouring, 2 m for clay (figure 3)

Figure -3. Transverse profiles of roads and paths in microdistricts

A-main two-lane road; B-main one-lane road; C - Secondary Road(

entrance to the house); g-pedestrian road; D-economic road

The planting design is an important part of the overall project for landscaping and landscaping the courtyard or garden of the residential group. The placement of trees and shrubs, open lawn areas and flower beds should be associated with the location of the areas, their size and configuration. In the residential area of the garden or yard, specific requirements are imposed on the greening of individual plots. Particular attention should be paid to the landscaping of local lines, as they emphasize the entrance to the house, which will attract the daily attention of residents living on the first floors. According to the standards and rules of construction, their width is 3.5-8.0 m. it is suitable to place groups of compact shrubs in adjacent strips and independent trees with a small height, as well as install flower beds or small areas (2x2, 4x4m) for amateur floriculture. It is recommended to

group the bushes according to the time of flowering. On local lines, places for planting climbing plants should be provided, which will give an additional picture to the facades of buildings. It is also a method of gradual transition from building to area. Trees on the strips should not be closer than 5 m from the building, bushes — not closer than 1.5 m, otherwise the plants will shade the windows of the premises. The lines of the House should be inextricably linked with the entire territory of the garden.

When placing seedlings in sports fields, it should be taken into account that these places are a source of noise and dust, so they are usually insulated with fence fences. Along the fences, you can provide climbing plants (seats outside the area). It is recommended to plant fast-growing trees with a dense large crown along the perimeter of the territory (fig. 4). Placing plants in groups or rows will help protect the area from the wind. The width of the planting areas around the block of territories should be at least 10 m. Tree

species should be placed not closer than 2 m from the edge of the territory. This eliminates the unevenness of the light and the flickering of light spots on the coatings. Placement of plants around playgrounds, especially for preschool children, should be carried out taking into account wind protection, optimal lighting, as well as adequate ventilation. In addition, they must be separated from the paths with a planting line at least 3 m wide. To insulate playgrounds around the perimeter, shrubs (hedges, groups), trees should be provided to shade part of the cover of the fields from the South and Southwest. For this purpose, it is recommended to use combinations of plants with a dense (Maple, Linden) and openwork (ash, birch) Crown. In the southern regions (south of 55° N), 1/2 of the children's playgrounds should be shaded, in the regions of the middle lane — 1/3.

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